

OPTIONS FOR REDIRECTION TO THE MANDATORY DPP BACKUP (DPP SYSTEM)

Publication date	December 2024
Version	1
Contributors	Carolynn Bernier (CEA), Huib van Nieuwenhuijze (TNO), Staffan Olsson (GS1 Sweden), Simen Kjellberg (Kezzler), Attila Kun (DDCC), Henna Suomi (IOXIO), Tanel Tammet (Taltech), Jesper Kuiper (TNO), Marco Volpini (Extrared), Matthew Neibert (EON), Elyse Tosi (EON), Henna suomi (IOXIO), Kartik Chawla (TNO), Sjoerd Rongen (TNO), Claire Fioretti (Michelin), Georgi Stoyanov (Cobuilder)
Abstract	This document is a collection of opinions from members of the CIRPASS-2 consortium on options for the implementation of redirection service for access to the DPP backup data and respective pros & cons.
Citation	CIRPASS-2. (2024). Options for redirection to the mandatory DPP Backup (DPP System). CIRPASS-2 consortium. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15007842

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
1.	06/12/2024	Document finalization	

CIRPASS-2 CONSORTIUM

#	Participant Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
1	Commissariat A L'Energie Atomique Et Aux Energies Alternatives	CEA	France
2	Tallinna Tehnikaülikool	TALTECH	Estonia
3	Mindworks Industries Ou	MWX	Estonia
4	DIGITALEUROPE AISBL	DIGITALEUROPE	Belgium
5	E CIRCULAR APS	E CIRCULAR APS	Denmark
6	F6s Network Ireland Limited	F6S IE	Ireland
7	Global Textile Scheme GmbH	GTS	Germany
8	maki Consulting GmbH	MAKI	Germany
9	Ekodenge Muhendislik Mimarlik Danismanlik Ticaret Anonim Sirketi	EKODENGE	Sweden
10	Stiftelsen Chalmers Industriteknik	CIT	Sweden
11	Nederlandse Organisatie Voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek TNO	TNO	Netherlands
12	BIO Innovation Service SAS	BIOIS	France
13	Technische Universiteit DELFT	TU Delft	Netherlands
14	Asociacion De Empresas Tecnologicas INNOVALIA	INNOVALIA	Spain
15	CBT Comunicacion & Multimedia SL	CBT	Spain
16	Asociacion Para Desarrollo De La Economia Del Dato	BAIDATA	Spain
17	GS1 In Europe	GS1 IN EUROPE	Belgium
18	AOC Innovation	AOC INNOVATION	France
19	+IMPAKT Luxembourg SARL	+IMPAKT	Luxembourg
20	Industrie 4.0 Osterreich - Die Plattform Fur Intelligente Produktion	PIA	Austria
21	FUJITSU Technology Solutions	FJBE	Belgium
22	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Forderung Der Angewandten Forschung EV	Fraunhofer	Germany
23	Extra Red SRL	EXTRA RED SRL	Italy
24	European Apparel And Textile Confederation Aisbl	EURATEX	Belgium
25	IOXIO OY	IOXIO OY	Finland
26	Suomen Tekstiili Ja Muoti Ry	FINATEX	Finland
27	KEZZLER AS	Kezzler	Norway
28	EON Cloud Technology KFT	EON	Hungary
29	Avery Dennison Atma GmbH	atma.io	Austria
30	Circular.Fashion UG	circ.fashion	Germany
31	TRIPLER	TripleR	Belgium

32	SCANTRUST BV	SCANTRUST BV	Netherlands
33	ARCELIK A.S.	ARCELIK	Türkiye
34	WHATT.IO AB	whatt.io	Sweden
35	Gorenje Gospodinjski Aparati DOO	GORENJE	Slovenia
36	Hisense Gorenje Europe Poslovne Storitve DOO	HGE	Slovenia
37	Manufacture Francaise Des Pneumatiques MICHELIN	MICHELIN	France
38	COBUILDER AS	COBUILDER	Norway
39	DIN Deutsches Institut Fuer Normung EV	DIN e.V.	Germany
40	VDE Verband Der Elektrotechnik Elektronik Informationstechnik EV	VDE	Germany
41	Energy Web AG	Energy Web AG	Switzerland
42	WORLDLINE France	WORLDLINE FR	France
43	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt	PTB	Germany
44	Digital Data Chain Consortium GbR	DDCC	Germany
45	ZVEI e. V.	ZVEI e.V.	Germany
46	Association of Service and Computer Dealers International	ASCDI	US
47	Open Blockchain for Asset Disposition Alliance (OBADA)	OBADA	US
48	Green Electronics Council	GEC	US
49	Textile Exchange	TextileExchange	US
50	IPoint Systems GmbH	IPoint	Germany

Grant Agreement No.: 101158775
Call: DIGITAL-2023-CLOUD-DATA-04
Topic: DIGITAL-2023-CLOUD-DATA-04-DIGIPASS
Type of action: DIGITAL Simple Grants

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

© CIRPASS-2 Consortium, 2024-2027

Except otherwise noted, original content on this document is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence. This licence enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator. The licence allows for commercial use.

ABBREVIATIONS

CPR	Construction Products Regulation
DPP	Digital Product Passport
DPPSP	Digital Product Passport Service Provider
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
ESPR	Eco-design for Sustainable Product Regulation
IAA	Identification, Authentication, Authorization
ID	Identifier
MSA	Market Surveillance Authorities
REO	Responsible Economic Operator
SME	Small-Medium Enterprise
UPI	Unique Product Identifier

1 OBJECTIVE OF THIS DOCUMENT

This document is a collection of opinions from members of the CIRPASS-2 consortium on options for the implementation of the following aspect of the DPP system:

- Backup redirection services for access to DPP data in a manner that ensures data persistency and availability to all stakeholders with corresponding access rights.

The aim is to collect ideas and compare the respective advantages and disadvantages of the different approaches.

1.1 DISCLAIMER

The information provided in this presentation is for information purposes only. The CIRPASS-2 consortium partners are not responsible for any damage that could result from making use of this information.

Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, European Commission, or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union, the European Commission nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and should not be interpreted as reflecting those of CEN/CENELEC JTC 24.

2 BACKUP REDIRECTION SERVICE FOR PERSISTENCY AND AVAILABILITY

Options to ensure access to the DPP backup in case of cessation of activity of an economic operator in the European Union include the following:

Definitions

Web redirection service (also called http redirect): a web service understood in the sense of RFC 9110 section 15.4¹ in which a web service receives an URI as input and returns one or more URIs.

DNS redirection service: an internet service operated by a domain owner during which the resolution process for a subdomain host is modified.

2.1 OPTION 1: EUROPEAN COMMISSION OPERATES ONE OF MANY FALLBACK (I.E. DEFAULT) REDIRECTION SERVICES

In this scenario, the EC possesses a registry of every link to a DPP backup. The default (i.e. fallback) redirection service can be in the form of a smartphone app, a web application, a web portal, etc. This service is provided by, under the governance of the European Commission or voluntarily by many other organisations, or a combination of these. In case a user cannot access the active DPP copy, they use a fallback web redirection service, offered either by the EC or by other operators, to find the link to the backup copy. **Consumers are made aware of the existence of the fallback services (they are ‘informed users’) through consumer-focused information campaigns about the role and value of the DPP to consumers.**

Organisation	Comment (pros and cons)
CEA	<p>Pro: This is the option that was recommended by the CIRPASS consortium².</p> <p>Pro: Implementation of the fallback redirection service may rely either solely on the EC or alternatively be distributed to sector-specific industry associations or Producer Responsibility Organisations (or other organisation), under EC governance, or a combination of the two options. Indeed, it is likely that sector-specific professional organisations will have a strong interest in providing such fallback redirection services in the future, either in place of or in addition to the EC. Those services will have the effect that the EC redirection fallback will probably have very little traffic.</p> <p>Pro To limit the frequency of 'dead links' but also to lower implementation costs for economic operators, REOs should be encouraged to use pooled DPP services. This is naturally the case when a REO employs the services of a DPPSP. But such services could also be offered by industry associations or Producer Responsibility Organisations who are less susceptible to cessation of activity. These organisations can manage the switch to the backup copy smoothly, in place of the EC. It is likely that smaller economic operators will employ such pooled services to limit their costs, and that only larger, more stable, REOs will consider creating their own DPPs. Decentralized backup redirection services can therefore easily adapt to social and economic constructs, as industry evolves and cooperates.</p> <p>Pro: Looking towards the future, it is likely that other jurisdictions beyond the EU will want to also</p>

¹ <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc9110#name-redirection-3xx>

² Wenning, R., Papadakos, P., & Bernier, C. (2024). DPP System Architecture (V1.9). CIRPASS Consortium. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12206138>

	<p>develop a DPP with different mandatory information requirements than those defined by the EU. The European DPP system can be designed to also support international DPP systems and to automatically adapt the displayed mandatory information content depending on the user's location. The operation of cross-jurisdictional DPP systems, and international trade, would be facilitated by the absence of an EU server address hardcoded into the data carrier.</p> <p>Con: Access to the backup copy is not automatic if generalist applications (e.g. a non-DPP-aware web browser) are used to access the DPP. Luckily, these applications adapt quickly as needs arise. Furthermore, the DPP roll-out can be accompanied by consumer information campaigns such that consumers become "informed users" of the DPP service. This would mean that they are informed that a backup copy will necessarily exist for X numbers of years and can be found easily on the internet (e.g. possibly thanks to the EU Web Portal).</p>
DDCC	<p>Pro: From technical perspective this option is the most simple and stable one. And due to its simplicity, it will come with the lowest total costs.</p>
GS1	<p>Pro: This is still the most viable solution due to simplicity and no unnecessary EU involvement in the day-to-day operation of the DPP ecosystem (that will not only be used for DPP)</p>
TNO	<p>Pro: This approach enables scalability across political blocks with e.g. the Netherlands hosting a Dutch Backup redirection service, and the EU fallback redirection service serving as a fallback for that. Providing a clear path to decentralize again and lowering the reliance on this default redirection service.</p> <p>Con (minor): As there is no automatic redirect from an unavailable active copy to the next-in-line backup service, automated services that rely on access to a DPP can break and would require fixing to make them point to the correct backup link. However, because a lot of DPP data will be locally cached by downstream economic operators, such failures will be rare, and if they happen, the automated services can be programmed to automatically use a fallback redirection service.</p>
EON	<p>How It Works</p> <p>Registry Management:</p> <p>The EC maintains a registry with details of each company's primary and backup DPP data sources.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Example: <p>Primary DPP data source: matts-company.com/api/dpp/{insertID}</p> <p>Backup DPP data source: eon.xyz/dpp-backup/api/dpp/{insertID}</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scenarios: <p>Scenario 1: Users directly access primary DPP data through data carrier & weblinks (e.g., matts-company.com/id/123456).</p> <p>Scenario 2: EC DPP Web App retrieves DPP data by looking up the api from the EC registry and calls the company's Primary API (if presenting data in the webapp. Or it could redirect the user depending on the functionality of the EC DPP WebApp)</p> <p>Scenario 3: If the company goes out of business, the EC DPP Web App retrieves DPP data by looking up the api from the EC registry and queries the company's Backup DPP data source..</p> <p>Pros</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplicity: <p>The EC only manages a registry of data source links without directly hosting or redirecting traffic. Less overhead in terms of DNS or redirection infrastructure.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scalability: <p>Easy to scale as adding new companies only involves updating the registry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decentralization: <p>The DPP operators retain control of their primary and backup data sources.</p>

	<p>No need for the EC to manage subdomains or redirections directly.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost-Effective: Lower infrastructure costs compared to maintaining DNS or centralized redirection services. • Failover Handling: Backup data is accessible via a fallback mechanism managed by the registry. • Consumer Transparency: Direct links (e.g., matts-company.com) allow brands to maintain their consumer-facing presence. • Clarity in roles & responsibilities: With this set up, the EC is not responsible for any private sector needs in real-time as all can be done async and does not run the risk of interfering with standard business practices through the digital product – especially with the myriad of use cases that can be deployed from the digital product (which is the hope and vision of the EC). <p>Con: If not leveraging the EC DPP Web App and the REO goes out of business or the primary DPP is not available the user will need to leverage the EC DPP WebApp in order to retrieve the backup DPP.</p>
Taltech	<p>Pro: Absolutely support this option. The arguments have been made above. In our view the strongest arguments are expected support by companies (have both a right and a need to control their data), ease of implementation and simplicity.</p>
ExtraRed	<p>Pro: As already stated by the arguments above, this is the most straightforward and simple option in terms of costs and maintenance.</p> <p>Con: No automatic redirection to the backup DPP, but only if a DPP aware app is not used to access the DPP.</p>
Cobuilder	<p>Pro: This is the simplest solution. The link to the active DPP itself would or could be handled by a redirection service can be provided by either REO, Associations or DPPSPs. For the fallback option by the EC, it should be manageable since such a registry only holds the links to the backup.</p> <p>Con: Still, in terms of e.g. CPR (Construction Products Regulation), there could still be a lot of redirections, since 10 years after a product is taken off the market and up until 25 years, there will be a permanent redirection to a backup provider.</p>

2.2 OPTION 2: EUROPEAN COMMISSION MANAGES A DPP SYSTEM DOMAIN AND ALLOCATES SUBDOMAINS TO EACH DPP OPERATOR

In this scenario the EC would manage a specific domain to provide a stable backup redirection-like service for every DPP. Each organization hosting DPP's would receive its own subdomain in order to allow organisations to manage their own DPP web redirection services and repositories as they see fit. If we use the domain 'dpp.eu' as an example, this would result in domain names such as 'toycompany.dpp.eu' and 'bicyclefactory.dpp.eu'. When informed of cessation of activity, a "DNS redirection" approach could be used by the EC to transform a request to e.g. 'toycompany.dpp.eu' into a request to toycompany-backup.com to reach the backup DPP copy.

Organisation	Comment (pros and cons)
CEA	<p>Pro: This option enables automatic access to the DPP backup, assuming the EC is informed of the cessation of activity.</p> <p>Con: This option is equivalent to the EC operating a second internet inside of the internet. The EC would have to allocate subdomains for REOs who wish to host their own DPPs. This is identical to</p>

	<p>the activity of the ICANN (Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers) which manages the most widely used DNS root server. This will force the EC to reproduce a DNS-like system, creating naming conflicts and all the problems (security, privacy, hijacking, etc.) known from the DNS system. This will also force the EC to reproduce the costly redundancy architecture. For information, the redundancy required for the internet DNS is 200 servers distributed in 50 countries. Failure of this service would leave the EC liable for all economic damage caused to companies who wish to rely on the DPP system to exchange data for their operations relying on either mandatory or non-mandatory DPP information.</p> <p>Con: Broken links will remain if the EC is not informed of the cessation of activity. In this case, users will have no means to access the backup.</p> <p>Con: Because of the mandatory use of the EU-owned domain in the data carrier, the EU may create barriers to international trade.</p> <p>Con: Should this option be selected by the EC, economic operators will be scared by the risks related to single-point-of-failure and not use the DPP system for beyond-mandatory information exchange. This will force them to create a DPP to satisfy the bureaucratic requirement and create a second 'DPP', using a second data carrier on their products (similarly to what they are already doing today), hence creating a parallel DPP-like system but without the cross-sectorial interoperability features of the EU's DPP system. All of the potential benefits to industry of the DPP system will be lost and both costs and confusion will increase. The environmental cost of implementing the EU DPP system will also increase, at no additional benefit.</p>
TNO	<p>Con: This domain would provide a very attractive target for both 'denial of service' attacks and sophisticated attacks to gain access.</p> <p>Creating and maintaining the subdomains would require a lot of work, since many different entities, ranging from service providers to large companies and even parts of large companies, will wish to provide a DPP repository. The unavoidable changes in responsibility for DPP's, and thus domains, would require additional work.</p> <p>Making this work for cases in which only the product ID is known will require an interface (both a web interface and a machine-accessible interface) to determine the web link based on the product ID or the standardization of the URI structure to access a DPP, limiting the freedom of the issuing organization in the structure of their DPP web links.</p> <p>Con: The REO, or delegated party, hosting the DPP would need access to the data of the subdomain in order to register the actual web link for the DPP. Maintaining correct access rights for each subdomain is a large administrative burden, which would fall on the EC.</p>
DDCC	<p>Con: An EU specific domain to be used for the DPP will add a new region-specific label to the product, increasing complexity. Globally not harmonized product labelling causes significant costs in the supply chain and is a challenge specifically for SMEs. To ensure that no product without the correct labelling enters the European market when selling to a wholesaler, the manufacturer will have to label 100% of his products with the EU specific labelling, even when the product is intended to be sold in another world region.</p>
GS1	<p>Con: Any implementation adding more characters to be encoded in data carriers impact printing and scanning negatively.</p> <p>This solution risks giving too much data insights to the EU, since every QR of every scan would be recorded by the dpp.eu site. And also any other DPP query.</p>
IOXIO	<p>Con: Complementing the GS1 consideration regarding the "data insight" is that it would mean in practice that the EU could create insights on how much different products from different REOs are used based on requests being made to the DPPs which can be categorized as confidential information by the businesses which obviously shouldn't be known by the commission without a clear legal reason.</p>
EON	<p>How It Works</p> <p>Domain Structure:</p> <p>The EC manages a centralized domain (e.g., dpp.eu) and allocates subdomains to companies (e.g.,</p>

mattscompany.dpp.eu).

Redirection:

The EC DNS service points traffic from subdomains to companies' servers using DNS records (e.g., CNAME, TXT).

If a company's server is unavailable, the DNS redirects traffic to a backup server.

Scenarios:

Traffic to mattscompany.dpp.eu/id/123456 is redirected to the company's server or, if unavailable, to the backup server.

Pros

Automatic Fallback: DNS-based or application-level redirection ensures seamless failover to the backup source without user intervention provided that the EC registry knows the primary DPP is not available.

Cons

- Infrastructure Complexity:

Requires a robust DNS or redirection infrastructure capable of managing and monitoring thousands of subdomains.

DNS updates may take time to propagate, potentially delaying access during failovers.

- High Costs:

The EC must invest in and maintain extensive infrastructure for DNS management and redirection monitoring.

- Centralized:

Companies lose some autonomy as their DPP presence is tied to a subdomain controlled by the EC.

- Supporting private sector / financial implication:

As in #2 and #3, it is important to point out this scenario places the EC at the center of REO's business operations and must have resourcing to meet standard business SLAs (service level agreements) as lag in addressing critical issues will financially harm REOs in some cases, especially if the DPP is leveraging multiple use cases (not just the DPP base line data / functionality) which is the hopes of the EC.

- Scalability Concerns:

Managing DNS records for thousands of companies may pose scalability and administrative challenges.

- URI Structure:

The length of the subdomain/domain has direct impacts on the data carrier. (ie QR code size, memory for NFC, etc)

- Security:

Centralized and could be an attack vector (e.g. denial of service)

- Data Privacy:

A centralized system like dpp.eu risks collecting too much data about scans and queries, potentially giving the EC access to sensitive commercial and operational insights.

- Labelling Complexity for Global Markets:

Requiring EC -specific labels and domains will complicate global supply chains.

Taltech

Con: Clearly against this option. We support all the arguments above and see no need to add anything new. This option would be impossible to implement, for several independent reasons. For example, companies certainly want to use their own or preferred domain names, not the mycompany.dpp.eu. If they were required to use these, they would need to maintain the DNS

	service specially for this subdomain, which would be organizationally complex. Automatically “taking over” the non-functional subdomains by EU would be also highly complex and error-prone (how do we reliably understand that the original server is no more functional?). There is also no way to force non-EU companies to use such a scheme.
Cobuilder	<p>Pro: Fallback solution can be implemented</p> <p>Con: One point of failure, and as mentioned before, very likely to be a target for different attacks such as denial-of-service as one example.</p> <p>Con: For scalability and manageability, to administer such a solution would require high cost for the commission.</p> <p>Con: REOs may serve more markets than EU single market.</p>
ExtraRed	<p>Pro: Automatic redirection to the DPP backup regardless of whether a DPP aware app is used or not</p> <p>Con: In addition to the arguments above, this option seems to suffer the risk of subdomain takeover attacks.</p>

2.3 OPTION 3: EUROPEAN COMMISSION MANAGES ALL REDIRECTS FOR ALL DPP DATA REQUESTS CENTRALLY

Similarly to the previous option, in this scenario, the EC provides a stable redirection service for every DPP, in place of the REO (or its delegated DPPSP). However, in this scenario, the EC operates a web service, i.e. a registry of all DPP web links, including both the active web link and the link to the backup copy. An example domain for this link registry would be **www.DPPlinkregistry.eu**. Any URI embedded in any data carrier carried by a regulated product must link to this central redirection service which manages all DPP data requests, for example using **www.DPPlinkregistry.eu/UPI**. In the advent of cessation of activity of an economic operator (REO or DPPSP) or a change in DPPSP, the central service is informed when it should redirect to the active DPP or to the backup copy.

Organisation	Comment (pros and cons)
CEA	<p>Pro: Redirection to the backup copy would be automatic once cessation of activity is declared to EU services. However, to avoid situations of undeclared failures, the EC services would have to constantly crawl the URIs available to it.</p> <p>Con: This option creates a central critical infrastructure for the entire Circular Economy that is very vulnerable to attacks. In order to safeguard such a critical infrastructure against failure, the EU would have to continuously invest in a very expensive fail-safe system with large operational costs. Failure of this service would leave the EC liable for all economic damage caused to companies who wish to rely on the DPP system to exchange data for their operations relying on either mandatory or non-mandatory DPP information.</p> <p>Con: Should this option be selected by the EC, economic operators will be scared by the risks related to single-point-of-failure and not use the DPP system for beyond-mandatory information exchange. This will force them to create a DPP to satisfy the bureaucratic requirement and create a second ‘DPP’, using a second data carrier on their products (similarly to what they are already doing today), hence creating a parallel DPP-like system but without the cross-sectorial interoperability features of the EU’s DPP system. All of the potential benefits to industry of the DPP system will be lost and both costs and confusion will increase. The environmental cost of implementing the EU DPP system will also increase, at no additional benefit.</p> <p>Con: Existing and widely-used international standards for embedding UPIs into URLs, designed for business-friendliness, could not be used: IEC 61406-2 Identification Link, GS1 Digital Link, etc.</p> <p>Con: Seeing that some UPIs may actually already be URLs, this would require adding more</p>

	characters to be encoded in data carriers, impacting printing and scanning negatively.
TNO	<p>Con: The amount of regular traffic to this central registry will be massive and require a large investment in technical infrastructure.</p> <p>Con: This domain would provide a very attractive target for both 'denial of service' attacks and sophisticated attacks to gain access.</p> <p>Con: Mandating a central service enables the operator to gain very valuable insights in the EU market. This data is valuable and therefore an interesting target for bad actors. Additionally the possibility of surveillance could have a negative effect on the willingness of companies to make maximal use of the system. In addition to the risk to commercial secrecy, this may also carry significant risks to individual privacy, as this service may also have access to data regarding which consumer accessed the DPP of which product, and potentially also location data.</p>
GS1	<p>Con: This is similar to vendor-lock-in and challenging for existing service providers already offering resolver services.</p> <p>This is a single point of failure for the whole ecosystem.</p> <p>This enables regulators to control what additional data the product is allowed to link to (censorship). This type of implementations exist outside Europe in countries lacking EUs democratic values, which should not be seen as role models.</p>
MICHELIN	Con: nothing to add to all arguments already developed above...
IOXIO	Con: This would presumably hamper the competitiveness of the DPP service provider market and decrease incentives of various DPP application and other service developers to start and to run new businesses.
Cobuilder	<p>Pro: Fallback solution can be implemented. For CPR, EC will allow REOs to stop the responsibility of serving the DPP as a primary source, 10 years after product is off the market. The next 15 years, that would be the backup service provider's responsibility. To have one registry that has information about both primary and backup makes a permanent redirection fallback possible.</p> <p>Con: One point of failure, and as mentioned before, very likely to be a target for different attacks such as denial-of-service as one example.</p> <p>Con: Very high volume of requests must be taken into consideration when offering such a service.</p> <p>Con: REOs may serve more markets than EU single market.</p>
ExtraRed	Con: Nothing to add to the arguments made above.

2.4 OPTION 4: A DEDICATED EU AGENCY TAKES OVER DOMAIN NAMES FOR REDIRECTION SERVICES WHICH ARE NO LONGER IN OPERATION

In this scenario, whenever an economic operator that hosts an online redirection service stops operating on the EU market (a DPPSP or a REO), the ownership of the corresponding domain names is transferred to a dedicated agency, under the governance of the EC. The EC maintains the operation of the redirection service on these domains.

Organisation	Comment (pros and cons)
CEA	Con: The cessation of operation on the EU market does not always correspond to a cessation of activity. If the company domain is used for access to the redirection service, transferring the ownership of the domain name will not be possible.

GS1	Con: Not sure the EU can claim the right to purchase all domains from companies that go out of business, since domain name rules are not under EU (or any other government) governance.
TNO	Con: Unclear how this would be applied in cases of non-EU companies, that only put a product on the European market. The EU would have to seize domain names registered in non-EU countries.
IOXIO	Con: Does not allow the reuse of the domain names after the original REO has gone to bankruptcy. Domain names especially shorter ones have real business value and this option could harm the competition of the domain name market. Con: Very difficult (means expensive) to create the procedures to control this happens in practice
Cobuilder	Con: We believe the most relevant and obvious cons are already described above

2.5 OPTION 5: A TWO URL SOLUTION WITH CONSISTENT MAPPING

This option consists in defining two UPI-enabled URLs for each product, the first being defined exclusively by the REO and the second exploiting a redirection service operated by the EC (option 2 or 3 above).

Whatever the option chosen, there is a consistent and predictable mapping between the two URLs, so that the on-product URL, e.g., qr.example.com/identifier has a corresponding and persistent DPP redirection service address of qr.example.com.dpp.eu/identifier.

The first URL would be embedded by the REO onto the product or its packaging. To access the backup copy, consumers would require the use of a dedicated application.

The second URL would be used for automatic fallback in machine-to-machine information processing: integrations between systems, dedicated apps, rendering DPPs for eCommerce etc., preventing dead links in these cases.

Because this option still allows the REO to control the domain on their own products, this would be way less intrusive to the REOs of the private sector and allow them to better exploit the benefits also outside of regulation.

Organisation	Comment (pros and cons)
Kezzler	<p>Pro: Avoiding consumer confusion by having multiple carriers on the product to cater to both EEA and other markets with the same product (which would be the result of enforcing the link to lead to domain hosted by the EC).</p> <p>Pro: Avoiding separate planning, manufacturing and distribution for the EEA vs other markets (leading to overproduction as unintended negative ecological consequence)</p> <p>Pro: Less intrusive to the REOs of the private sector and allow them to better exploit the benefits also outside of regulation</p> <p>Pro: Still avoiding “a future web full of broken DPP links”</p> <p>Con: Slight inconvenience to the consumer, but only for product of companies no longer being in operation</p>
IOXIO	EU taking their correct role in supporting the functions for the back-up persistency but not intervening too much how market develops the main DPPs which in any case will be the majority of the use.
TNO	Con: The advantages over option 1 do not seem to warrant the cost of the EU managing an

	additional DNS server.
ExtraRed	Con: This option seems to need the use of a DPP aware application for a consumer scanning a QR code of product from a company that is no more operating as Option 1. But comparing to it, it adds more complexity for the different handling of consumer oriented URL and machine-readable ones.
CEA	Con: This option combines both the inconveniences of Option 1, 2 and 3. The only slight improvement versus option 1 is that machine-to-machine applications do not have to be programmed to know the address of the fallback redirection service.